

POSITIVE PSYCHOLOGY INTERVENTION AND THE EMOTIONAL CHANGE AMONG GRADE TEN STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The study was intended to help the emotional change of the students in terms of increased self-esteem, improved relationship and positive outlook in life through positive psychology intervention. The descriptive research design and researcher made survey questionnaire were used in gathering and collecting of data. The mean, standard deviation, and Pearson-r correlation were used to analyze the result. The research included 100 respondents from 4 sections in the grades 10 of Col. Lauro D. Dizon Memorial Integrated High School. The study shown that positive psychology intervention such as mindful, gratitude exercise, kindness boosters, optimistic and spirituality may contribute to the emotional change of the students. Results indicates the significant relationship between the positive psychology intervention and the emotional change among grade ten students. This entails that these are important features to contemplate in the guidance program, in the classroom set up, even at home, to guide the students' emotional change. The findings concluded that hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the guidance and counseling program related factors and the students' personality development is not supported by evidence; hence, it is not sustained. Based on the study the following are hereby recommended that: (1) Guidance can implement positive psychology intervention. This may enable them to include on their school programs and other activities that would help other student's needs. (2)Adolescence students, this may enable them to become hopeful and spiritually strong to manage their emotions and have the capabilities to cope up stress in different situations especially on this new normal. (3) Teachers may encourage the students to apply the positive psychology intervention to their students to avoid the annoying situations, and it can entices positive emotion to the students and it may develop a good relationship between teacher and students and to other students as well. (4) Family could be practice the intervention, it may help the parents of these young people to become at peace, and lessen anxiety when it comes to their children whose experiencing pressure and struggles on their adolescence period. (5) The outcome of these studies may provide other researchers who will perform the same study of additional details. Moreover, the researcher is looking forward for potential researchers to understand the value of positive psychology in school environments, thus enhancing their academic performance, increased self-esteem of the students and improved relationships.

Keywords: mindful, gratitude exercise, kindness boosters, optimistic, spirituality, increased self-esteem, improved relationships and outlook in life.